

ASPECTS OF PULMONARY VESSEL MORPHOLOGY DURING CORONAVIRUS INFECTION

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Abstract

In this article, morphological changes in the walls of the pulmonary vessels, caused by the infectious disease of COVID-19, have been studied. During the 2021 pandemic, pieces of the lungs of people who died from the disease were taken from areas rich in blood vessels and studied histologically. It is known that the abundance of the ACE2 enzyme in the endothelium of the pulmonary vessels, their extensive damage by SARS-CoV-2, the development of a strong and diffuse discirculatory process, which continues with the appearance of endotheliosis, endothelitis, coagulopathy, and vasculitis. , thrombotic microvasculitis, leads to the development of diffuse hemorrhagic inflammation in the lung tissue. Initially, all the blood vessels of the lung tissue become overfilled with blood, and diapedesis develops with hemorrhages in the alveoli. The development of fibrinoid swelling and fibrinoid necrosis, endothelitis in the wall of the pulmonary vessels, the appearance of blood clots in large and small vessels is a manifestation of macro- and microangiopathy. During the proliferative period of COVID-19, lymphohistiocytic infiltration and, finally, sclerosis are detected in and around the walls of blood vessels.

Key words: COVID-19, lungs, blood vessels, fibrinoid necrosis, thrombosis, microangiopathy, hemorrhage.

Relevance

The pathogenesis, morphogenesis and pathomorphology of vascular damage in COVID-19 is the fundamental basis of lung damage. It is known that the SARS-CoV-2 virus has a tropism against the vascular endothelium without having a cytopathic effect on various types of cells, which aggravates alveolar tissue damage (1, 2, 3, 4). In the studies conducted in 2020-2022, microscopic changes in pulmonary vascular lesions were mainly studied. At the same time, issues of local and systemic damage of blood vessels, microangiopathy, vasculitis and endotheliitis are being discussed, and questions about the mechanism of their development remain open. In future pathoanatomical studies, as a result of

the use of histological, histochemical and immunohistochemical methods, it is necessary to study the alterative, inflammatory, reparative processes in the blood vessel wall and the occurrence of neoangiogenesis in different periods of infection. the reasons are likely to be revealed. According to the literature, thrombi appear in almost all branches of the pulmonary artery, including segmental, segmental, subsegmental, and microcirculatory veins (9, 10, 11). The main part of the pulmonary artery is damaged in 13.5%, medium and small branches in 100% of cases. Due to the thickening of the walls of blood vessels due to swelling and inflammation under the influence of coronavirus, the destruction and necrosis of the lung tissue increases. Hypoxia developed as a result of impaired vascular perfusion leads to the activation of endothelium and platelets, as a result of which pathological factors increase. In addition, inflammatory cytokines disrupt the integrity of the endothelium and lead to the development of microangiopathy.

Materials and methods

As a research material, 28 of those who died of pneumonia caused by the coronavirus during the pandemic period in August-September 2021 were dissected and examined by the autopsy method at the Uz SSV Republican Pathological Anatomy Center. During the autopsy, samples were taken from all internal organs, including the lungs, for histological examination. The sections were processed in the usual way and paraffin blocks were prepared. Histological sections were taken from it and stained with hematoxylin and eosin. It was studied under a light microscope and the necessary areas were photographed. For the preparation of this article, histological sections from the lungs were studied in 10, 20, 40 objects of a light microscope, and microphotographs were taken that show the most significant pathomorphological changes that develop in the blood vessels of the lung tissue under the influence of the coronavirus.

Results and discussion

COVID-19 infection is an acute infection caused by a coronavirus, the causative agent of which is the SARS-CoV-2 ACE2 enzyme, which has a cytotoxic effect on all existing cells, including most cells of the lung tissue. The abundance of the ACE2 enzyme in the endothelium of pulmonary blood vessels continues with the development of a strong and scattered discirculation process, which continues with their extensive damage, endotheliosis, endotheliitis, coagulopathy, the formation of blood clots, vasculitis, microvasculitis. Coagulopathy in the form of microangiopathy and microthrombi leads to bleeding from almost all blood vessels and develops diffuse hemorrhagic inflammation in lung tissue. When the

lungs of those who died from the infection of COVID-19 were studied morphologically, the following changes were found. It is determined that all the blood vessels of the lungs, including pulmonary artery branches, bronchial artery branches, and pulmonary vein branches, are almost equally expanded, filled with blood, blood is poured around the small blood vessels, and the wall of the alveolar space is thickened due to scattered and diffuse hemorrhage. When studied under a microscope lens, it is observed that all the capillaries in the wall of the alveolar space have expanded sharply, almost all of them have been filled with blood by diapedesis, as a result, the alveolar wall has thickened and deformed, and foci of dystelectasis have appeared. As a result of the infection of COVID-19, the pathomorphological changes developed in the wall of the pulmonary blood vessels deepen, all layers of the vessel wall are destroyed, the vessel loses its shape, the cavity narrows, and fragments of endothelium, basement membrane, and even pericyte cells fall into it. During the second proliferation period of the COVID-19 infection, the proliferation of lymphohistiocytic cells is observed between the walls of blood vessels and alveoli in the lung tissue. This is confirmed by the fact that the blood in the vessel cavity, that is, part of the erythrocytes is adhered to the inner surface of the wall. It is determined that an infiltrate consisting of mainly lymphoid and macrophage cells has appeared around this blood vessel. In this case, it is observed that the inner endothelium layer has completely migrated, the basement membrane has become thinned and deformed, several tufts have appeared, several muscle tufts have appeared due to the proliferation of smooth muscle cells in the muscle layer. An infiltrate of lymphoid and histiocytic cells is found in the outer adventitial layer.

The proliferative period of the infection of COVID-19 is eventually observed in all structures of the lung tissue with the appearance of connective tissue tufts due to the proliferation of histiocytic cells. In this photomicrograph, it is determined that the connective tissue tufts around the blood vessels have appeared in a circular and chaotic manner. As a result, it is determined that the vascular cavity is narrowed, the endothelial layer is destroyed and migrated. In addition, infiltration of lympho-histiocytic cells, growth of connective tissue, as a result of which the lung tissue becomes dense, carnified, and airless, is also found in other areas of the lung tissue.

Summary

1. Changes in the lungs during COVID-19 infection proceed in several stages: in the first stage, all the blood vessels of the lung tissue are suddenly filled, leading

to the development of diffuse hemorrhagic inflammation due to diapedesis hemorrhages and hemorrhage in the alveoli.

2. In the exudative stage, the development of fibrinoid swelling and fibrinoid necrosis and endotheliitis in the wall of pulmonary blood vessels is manifested by the appearance of thrombus in both large and small vessels, and the development of macro- and microangiopathy.

3. During the proliferative period of COVID-19, lympho-histiocytic infiltration, and finally sclerosing, are found in and around the walls of blood vessels, then in the walls of alveoli.

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